

BEHAVIOURAL DISSONANCE IN THE CHANGE AGENTS' EFFORT OF THE RE-ENTRANTS: IMPLICATION FOR TRANSFER OF KNOWLEDGE

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Abstract

Human resources are the most valuable assets of an establishment. Training therefore plays a vital role in the life of an establishment. Re-entrants from training had to do with recipients undergoing training and on return they are absorbed properly into the establishment, thereby applying the newly acquired skills for the development of the establishment. This research work is hinged on the fact that recipients suffer deprivation and neglect on return from training as it was observed by the researchers. This of course leads to lack of commitment and negative attitudes in places of work. This study is an empirical one, which derived its data from primary source through the administration of questionnaires. The two ministries used in this study are the Ministry of Justice and the Ministry of Information, both situated in Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria. This work revealed that some civil servants do not enjoy the privilege of embarking on training as at when due because government does not encourage training and re-training of personnel. It was also observed that some civil servants have spent about ten years or more in their various establishments, and had not had the opportunity to undergo training. The paper submits that there is an ample need for training and subsequent placement as it sets a worker up in identifying his/her potentials and contributing to the growth of the establishment

Background of Study

Following the attainment of self-rule by Nigeria in 1960, the need arose for skilled manpower to handle the development plans and demands of the country. It thus dawned on the politicians that the public service cannot effectively sustain the drive for modernization and development without trained and experienced workforce. Thus, in 1967, the Federal Government commissioned a survey of "The Training Needs of the Federal Civil Service". This was carried out by the Institute of Public Administration of the then University of Ife. According to Onasanya (1999:208-10) the survey noted that "there is an acute shortage of trained personnel in the administrative and professional cadres or groups in the service". This revealed an urgent need for "systematic, sustained and regular program" of training in the civil service. Similarly, training was recognized as a strategy for meeting the manpower required for the implementation of the Third National Development Plan 1975-1979. The impetus for training and the need to increase its pace became more evident with the government's acceptance of the report of the Udoji Reforms which observed that the major constraint to development in the country was the lack of skilled and experienced manpower to carry out the required tasks. It, therefore, recommended systematic training as a means of meeting the manpower shortage in the public service.

Training has been viewed as a panacea for most organisational problems. The tendency is to see training as bringing about the needed change in the recipient of the training and by implication, in the organisation also. Thus, training is seen as producing a permanent change both in the level of knowledge, skills and attitude of the recipients (Davis, 1972). All these, it is hoped, will impact positively on the organisation through improved performance, productivity and responsiveness. The recipient of the training programme thus becomes a change agent in the organisation. He is expected to transfer what he had learnt to the organisation and therefore initiates the needed change in performance and productivity of the organisation. In this respect, certain improvement is expected and this is usually seen as connoting standards of fulfilment of expectations and deviations from this expected improved standard which is frowned at.

However, what is not usually taken into consideration before an organisational member is sent for training is the training recipient's own fears, hopes, expectations and perceptions of the training despite the fact that these constitute major factors that may influence, motivate and even inhibit learning and hence the transfer of learning to the work situation. Dissonant behaviour occurs as a result of the recipient's failure to transfer learning (knowledge) to the work situation and thus fulfil his change agent expectation. Dissonant behaviour is therefore not consistent with the organisational expectation and occurs as a result of the training recipient's failure or inability to induce or carry out his expected role as a change agent on re-entry from a training programme. In earlier studies, Mmobuosi (1989) had pointed out that the inclination to induce change by transferring knowledge gained from the training to the work situation is not a function of sex, age, academic and professional qualifications; rather Gibb (1977) has associated

it with the organisational climate, the training recipient's supervisor's disposition and other organisational members' behaviour. However, very prominent is the training recipient's own perception of the training programme and his attitudinal disposition to want to transfer or share knowledge gained from the training attended (Makinde & Agara, 1992).

The civil service according to Adu (1977) is comprised of persons other than holders of political or judicial officers, who are employed in a civil capacity and whose remuneration is paid wholly and directly out of money voted by parliament or legislature. Ejere & Idise (1996) argued that this definition appears too broad as it tends to give the impression that all civilian employees in government, apart from members of the judiciary, are civil servants. Nwosu (1974) captures this distinction, as covering those public servants who are direct employees of the federal and state government, other than the police, the armed forces personnel, the judicial personnel and the teachers. However, both civil and public services are similar in their bureaucratic character and all members of the public and civil services are employees of the government (Ejere & Idise, 1996). Thus the greatest waste in any establishment is the failure to recognize and use the abilities of people, and to recognize that it is people who produce the strategy, structure, systems and styles of the establishment. Adebayo (2008) argued that it is a mark of poor administration for a top administrator to seek to handle by himself all the essential assignments in the department.

The need for recognition of the importance of the worker and his needs are even more critical for service-oriented establishment, such as the public service. However, while the systems approach which would analytically seek the best solutions to our public problems is gaining prominence in both administrative and academic circles, the emphasis upon processes and procedure continues. As a result, the public service seems incapacitated in its ability to drive rapid growth and improved quality of life for all, including the same public servants. Consequently, the growing distrust of established and traditional routines and procedures which has failed to provide solutions, demonstrates that a paradigm shift is imperative. This concern was aptly illustrated by the Public Service Review Commission when it said: 'The public service is plagued by problems of corruption, adversary relationship and jealousy, inadequate delegation of responsibility, elitism or hierarchy, low consideration for time, low harmony and fear of insecurity' (Tunji, 2008). This concern also made Adebayo (2008) to regard the term bureaucracy to have acquired an odious connotation that is associated with inefficiency, lack of initiative, unintelligent rigidity in the approach to human problems, undue fussiness and bossiness on the part of officials and downright stubbornness. As it is today, the list of complaints against the Nigeria bureaucracy is both long and complex (Ofotokun, 2005).

Objective of Study

The objectives of this study are amongst others;

- identify the problem civil servants face after undergoing training,

- the attitude of immediate boss to those who underwent training, and
- assess the impact of training and self development of civil servant on their jobs in the establishment.

The hypotheses tested, were derived from the objectives above.

Research Method

This study is an empirical one, which derived its data from primary source through the administration of questionnaire. The two ministries used in this study are the Ministry of Justice and the Ministry of Information, Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria. These two ministries were selected because of the enormous task they perform in the discharge of duties in Edo State civil service and Nigeria in general. Civil servants in these ministries are expected to be well enlightened.

The research instrument for this study was administered to 130 persons in the establishments using random sampling technique of which 119 questionnaires were retrieved for data analysis. These were persons mostly in the senior staff category. That is from grade level eight (G.L8) and above. The data collected were arranged according to responses. The responses were therefore converted into figures by the use of tables (except in the case of open ended questions), and at the end of each table, there was discussion of findings using simple percentages, based on the hypothesis of the study.

Literature Review

The effective development of the human resources of an enterprise is one of the most vital contributions to the future and long-term growth of development and survival of any establishment. Oghators (2004:82) quote on Henry Gantt observed that workers should be trained in the habit of industry and co-operation.

However, to train people in attitudes may prove difficult because at the time people seek employment, they may have developed certain basic attitudes. In addition, attitudes are deep-rooted in people and cannot easily be changed. Attempts should be made by organisations, because the effect of negative attitude to work is disastrous (Okoh, 2005).

There is no gainsaying the fact that managements of enterprises are aware of the power of training, which is to modify, motivate, educate and improve the quality of their human resources, yet it is one of the most ill-managed and haphazardly handled areas. Oghator (2004:84) quoted Henry Fayol a scientific management thinker, when he observed that: "management was an activity common to all human undertakings and that the distinction between management as an activity, confined to conducting industrial and commercial undertakings, in public administration which is the act of conducting governmental activities which could be false and misleading". To the worker, training provides him with new skills that will enable promotion, redeployment and re-employment in cases of redundancy. Apart from that, training helps employees to grow and

develop into more responsible positions. This could be the reason why Omorogbe (2008: 158) wrote that "Socrates was convinced that the goal of human life is happiness and that the only way to attain it is through living a virtuous life based on knowledge".

In the work of Zaltman (1973) the acquisition of new skills by civil servants in the service, leads to "innovation". An Innovation is a new idea, which may be a recombination of old ideas, a scheme that challenges the present order, a formula, or a unique approach which is perceived as new by the individual involved. Leavitt (1965: 1144-1170) asserted that most innovations involve new technical and administrative components. He acknowledged the contributions from Ruttan and Hayami (1984:203-223) that posited that, many technological innovations in agriculture and elsewhere could not have occurred without innovations in institutional and organizational arrangements. So also, the likely success of developments in decision support systems by managements scientists largely hinges on an appreciation of the interdependence between technological hardware and software innovations on the one hand, and new theories of administrative choice behaviour on the other, while learning to understand the close connection between technical and administrative dimensions of innovations is a key part of understanding the management of innovation. Leavitt (1965: 133) in quoting Kimberly rightly points out that a positive bias pervades the study of innovation. Innovation is often viewed as a good thing because the new idea must be useful-profitable, constructive, or solve a problem. New ideas that are not perceived as useful are not normally called innovations; they are usually called mistakes. Objectively, of course the usefulness of an idea can only be determined after the innovation process is completed and implemented. Moreover, while many new ideas are proposed in organizations, only a very few receive serious consideration and developmental effort (Wilson, 1996). People become attached to ideas over time through a social-political process of putting their ideas into good use. It was with regard to these that Omorogbe (2008:163) referenced Plato in his write-up that "when reason is in control of the whole man and all human activities, then all virtues are present".

Theoretical Framework

This study will be better illustrated with the concept of Max Weber's theory of Bureaucracy. Max viewed bureaucracy as the most rational form of organisational technique superior to all other forms. He said that its rationality consisted of the application of precise techniques of legal standards and financial accounting to work of government, which was achieved organizationally through hierarchy of offices and the detachment of bureaucrats from any personal interest in the results of the decisions (Weber, 1948). While Adebayo (2008) thought differently, as he argued that bureaucracy is associated with inefficiency, lack of initiative, unintelligent rigidity in the approach to human problems, undue fussiness and bossiness on the part of officials and downright stubbornness. Consequently, the paper is of the view that Adebayo was indeed making reference to the fact that re-entrants from training are not subsequently absorbed or allowed to transfer knowledge gained after completion of training. As the newly acquired skill was meant to be applied for the development and growth of the establishment.

However, Weber advocated for pursuit of freedom for man, as he rightly noted that man was unduly being exploited. To this end, bureaucracy has been presented as an opportunity for the division of labour amongst workers, with a consisted pattern of recruitment and style leading to career building. The hierarchy amongst officers as propounded by Max paved the way for formal and informal network that connects organisational actors to one another through flows of information and cooperation. Tonwe (1998) agreed that Max was a highly perceived observer who first noticed the dynamics of bureaucracy in the emergent large organization after the industrial revolution in 1900 and he made unequalled effort to analyze the concept and dynamics of bureaucracy so much so that he was regarded as the father of bureaucracy.

General Characteristics of Respondents
Data Analysis and Discussion of Findings

Table 1: Age of Respondents

Social characteristic of	Respondent	Total
Age	20-30yrs – 31- – 41yrs and above 74 31 14 62.18 % 26.05% 11.76%	119
Sex	Male Female 64 55 53.7% 46.2%	119
Marital Status	Unmarried Married Divorced 71 41 7 56.66% 34.45% 5.88%	119
Qualification	Primary/post primary Secondary Tertiary 9 64 46 7.5% 53.78% 38.65%	119

The returned questionnaire shows that seventy four (62.18%) of respondents are within the age bracket of 20-30 years and thirty one (26.05%) respondents are in the age bracket of 31-40 years. Only fourteen (11.76%) respondents are 41 years and above. In view of these, if the productive age in the civil service is said to be 35 years then the group representing 62.18% should receive adequate training for excellent performance. According Onasanya (1999). progression

along the age rate is based on the assumptions that the value the enterprise attaches to the staff is directly related to the experience or maturity of the staff on the job.

Sex respondents show male dominance in the two ministries under investigation. There are sixty four (53.7%) male and fifty five (46.2%) female personnel in the ministries. This could be the reason why there are few female personnel in managerial positions in the civil service and the demand by the female folks for gender equality in governance and administration. Qualification of staff from the two ministries under study has nine (7.5%) respondents with primary/post primary education, sixty four (53.78%) respondents with secondary education while forty six (38.65%) respondents have tertiary education. In view of these, qualified personnel in the ministries are inadequate especially as these ministries play vital role in the administration of justice and in the dissemination of information to the general public. Without education there can be no training and without the two, there can be no development. In the model of development, the true professional must continually update his knowledge and re-educate himself by reading professional journals, attendance at conferences, refresher courses, and by intellectual contact with his colleagues such as the deployment of sensitivity training group or T- group training, Argyris (1957).

Data gathered on marital status of personnel in the ministries under investigation revealed that there are more unmarried people in the ministries. A total number of seventy one (59.66%) respondents are unmarried, while forty-one (34.45%) respondents were married. Seven (5.88%) were once married.

Main research questions:

Table 5: Question: How long have you been in the civil service?

1-10 yrs	11-20yrs	20yrs & above	Total
78	33	8	119
65.55%	27.73%	6.72%	

Interpretation: Table 5 shows that seventy eight (65.55%) respondents in the ministries had served in the ministries for between 1-10 years and thirty three (27.73%) have served for between 11-20 years. Only eight (6.72%) respondents have served for 20 years and above. There is need for the civil servants to develop collaborative effort were high competence at every level of government will be achieved. Adequate training, re-training and subsequent placement should be encouraged. There is also the need to strengthen the relevant regulatory agencies in order to ensure the enforcement of appropriate standards and entrench the principle of discipline in service. While Omorogbe (:2008: 115), on citing John Hoppers said that rewarding people according to their achievement also has the advantage of encouraging productivity.

Table 6 Question: Have you undergone any form of training in the Civil Service?

Yes	No	No Response	Total
27	87	5	119
22.68%	73.11%	4.20%	

Interpretation: Table 6 shows that twenty seven (22.68%) respondents agreed to have undergone training. Eighty seven (73.11 %) said they have not undergone training, while Training is an area where the investment yields more for the productivity of an individual to the enterprise. Surprisingly, in most governmental establishments, training is regarded as expensive, luxurious and wasteful. Some even argue that they cannot release their workers, especially their executives, querying "who will do his work during his absence"? Some reasons adduced from respondents who felt the need to do so, was that they have not been selected. Twenty Three (23) respondents believe it is not yet time for them to go on training, fifteen (15) respondents based it on management decision, eight (8) respondents said they are yet to apply for training. Ten (10) respondents said they believe that training of personnel in the service has to do with the number of years put into service; while the remaining thirty (30) respondents based it on nonchalant attitude of departmental heads and sometimes favoritism in the civil service. The reasons from respondents show that there is ignorance ascribed to the meaning of training. It was also observed that bosses do not encourage their subordinates to improve their skills and knowledge. This has made the subordinates feel that embarking on training or re-training is a wasteful venture.

Table 7: Question: If "Yes" to no.6 above what informed your decision to undergo training

(better performance)	(Knowledge based)	Responses gathered in the affirmative
14	15	29 (24.36%)

To this end, twenty nine (24.36%) responses were gathered. 14 respondents said it was to enhance better performance on their job. Others said it was knowledge based. Efficiency on the job is very important this is meant to test the depth of knowledge, achievement, dexterity and experience of the personnel in the job. For the fact that only 24.36% responded in the affirmative, shows that the civil service is indeed lacking the basic requirement and technical *know-how* to discharge its functions. The deprivation being suffered by the lack of opportunity to transfer knowledge gained by change agents can be better explained with the bureaucratic bottleneck and administrative corruption by bosses in most establishment. Evidently, new skills acquired by changed agents are not adequately transferred thereby hampering re-deployment, promotion, re-employment and in some cases discipline in the Service.

Table 8: Question: Was the training relevant to your job? A. Yes B. No

Yes	No	No Response
32(26.8%)	1(0.84%)	86 (72.27%)

Respondents to this question were quite few compared to the number of questionnaires that were

administered. Thirty two (26.8%) respondents answered in the affirmative. While a vast majority of eighty six (72.27%) declined to respond to the question. Only one (0.84%) said the training was not relevant. Obviously, there seems to be a consensus that training does not lead to motivation or proper placement of staff on return in the ministries. If this is correct, it means that staff moral is low while corruption and discouragement persist. In essence therefore, Tonwe (2004: 190) in quoting Idahosa and kpekpe, observed that, "training and performance evaluation are some of the features of personnel management in a typical bureaucratic organisation like the public service as it was asserted that if they are not properly managed, the attainment of organisational goals may be difficult".

Table 9. Question: Were you adequately placed in the right position on your return from training? a. Yes; b. No

Yes	No.	Number that declined to Respond
26 (21.84%)	6 (5.04)	87(73.11 %)

Proper placement of trained agents is a necessity in an establishment as it goes a long way to motivate and curb excesses. Twenty six (21.84%) responded in the affirmative and eighty seven (73.11%) declined to respond while Six (5.04%) said no. The paper further submits that "there is a gap between what a worker can do and what he should be able to do". The end product of training is the acquisition of new knowledge and skills which will greatly improve the output or productivity of the recipient. Where this happens, the organization will no doubt, be the better for it. But in a situation where workers are insufficiently trained or not trained at all, much should not be expected of them in terms of productivity. This is because they are stale, conservative, unimaginative and bereft of new ideas. It would be asking too much if it expected from them to perform as close as possible to their potential abilities. Indeed, such an expectation (if it does exist) is not only tantamount to wishful thinking but smacks of an attempt to reap wheat where one did not sow.

Table 10. Question: Does the government encourage staff development/training in the civil service? a. Yes; b. No

Yes	No.	No comment
55(46.22%)	3(2.52%)	61(51.26%)

Fifty five (46.22%) responses were in the affirmative. Three (2.52%) said that acquisition of new skills is not encouraged by the government, perhaps due to vacuum if the staff should go on training. Sixty one (51.26%) declined to comment. The analysis indicates that most government sectors are not sensitive to the development of manpower training. Encouragement of staff development through training ought to be one of the cardinal objectives of an establishment as it builds workers physically, morally and mentally which also improved interaction and communication between workers and the public. Often too, some departmental heads looked at the cost implications, which include amongst others training fees, cost of training equipment,

transportation cost, catering cost, library cost, statutory charges, miscellaneous training expenses or overhead charges. Thus there is an atmosphere of rigidity and discouragement for subordinates in the public service.

Table 11. Question: Have you been able to apply knowledge gained from training?

a. Yes; b. No

Yes	Number that did not Respond	Number that said No
23(19.33%)	91(76.47%)	5(4.20%)

Knowledge is said to be power. Training builds a worker with enough confidence and expertise in human relations and other related activities. The responses gathered on the above question revealed that twenty three (19.33%) agreed to have utilized training gained. This percentage is not enough to bring out the best in the service, as governmental policies ought to be carried out/implemented by majority of experienced and well-articulated personnel. Else the 19.33% who have utilized their training were handpicked without recourse, either to the individual or corporate needs. Ninety one (76.47%) declined to comment. Only five (4.20%) said they have not been able to apply knowledge gained. The 76.47% who were silent may have not had the opportunity of being selected to undergo training.

Table 12: Question: Do you know of any problem(s) associated with the staff placement after due completion of the training? A. Yes B. No

Number that commented	No Response
30 (25.21%)	89 (74.78%)

This was an open ended question. There was no response from eighty nine (74.78%) respondents. Meanwhile, in summary, thirty (25.21 %) commented as follows:

- lack of finance and equipment is a major factor;
- no vacancy available in the department, due to over staffing;
- no incentive or encouragement from the establishment;
- some say that lack of government response to the provision of modern technological, like computers, internet facilities etc, is a hindrance.
- some sectors lack focus and proper goal setting
- some say there is so much bureaucracy; and others say
- proper structure is not in place, to re-absorb workers.

From the above responses, it could be seen that staff in some establishments are not encouraged to go for training, while some that went for training (either sponsored or by personnel effort) find it difficult to be re-absorbed into the proper position. This has led to ineffectiveness, inefficiency, lack of commitment and lack of zeal to the discharge of duties. It is imperative to also state that workers suffer neglect in establishment while corruption is encouraged.

Summary of Findings and Conclusion

This study revealed that civil servants take a serious exception to the present situation of most establishments' insensitivity to training and re-entry. Mention must be made of the fact that when staff undergo training and they are not properly absorbed into the proper position on return, it brings about attitudinal problem and lack of confidence in the establishment. These transcend into the way governmental policies are handled. Hobbes (1946:78) wrote that, there can be no development and progress of an individual if social responsibility and self-control is lacking as moral laxity, egoism, individualism, lack of sense of duty, bribery and corruption, egoistic disregard for public well-being, embezzlement of public funds, etc, prevail. While some bosses have also used the opportunity of selection for training as an instrument of vengeance against subordinate, whose views were at variance with theirs, thereby rendering the newly acquired skills unproductive. Max Weber's theory on expert training recommends that training is required to effect quantitative and qualitative improvements in the performance of job. This he said helps employees to make better and quicker decisions and this catalyses efficiency in all the units of an establishment.

Furthermore, the study observed that staff training is lukewarm. The presence of an elaborate training programme is not indicative of commitment of management to its religious duties. It is not an overstatement to say that training programme is merely on paper. In practice, training (where there is at all) is done more or less on an *ad hoc* basis. The number of civil servants who benefit from training in a year is infinitesimal. In fact, the study did reveal that majority of the respondents have not benefited from any type of training since joining the establishment. The point that must be emphasized is that even when workers are not promoted, they ought to be trained on a routine basis to improve their knowledge and skills while they are absorbed properly. This has a tremendous advantage as it makes them effective and efficient in the performance of their duties. It is also expected that the result of this research work would serve as a working paper for the government and those who may wish to research on a similar area, in addressing economic performance, public accountability and other pressing issues as regards training and proper placement.

Recommendations

The training and development of existing employees have become important in a dynamic environment like the public service.

- Thus, the personnel department in close association with the other line managers should work out a planned and systematic training method for each category of staff to participate, i.e, selection for training should be on a routine basis, in this way majority of the staff members would be affected positively. As Scott (1975:45) quoted Maslow, as he once argued that "man is not simply a product of his past experience and learning, but forward-looking, self-directed and capable of shaping his own destiny and behaviour".
- In a bureaucratic organization like the civil service, there is a complete depersonalization of inter-personal relations. Formal dealings are encouraged to ensure that emotions and sentiments do not unduly interfere with the rationality and objectivity of officials. Offiong

(2004:216) in quoting Herzberg held that these factors (*emotion and sentiments*) will not produce growth in a worker's output capacity but will merely prevent a decline in his productivity. Rationality, objectivity and efficiency in decision-making are achieved by ensuring that all decisions are shaped by existing precedents, rules and regulations.

- The need for a holistic transformation of the Nigerian state has assumed an urgent and crucial dimension in the course of the last two decades. Civil servants who had undergone training did so for self-development, which sets them up by giving them the opportunity which allows them to develop their newly acquired skills and unfettered growth for the development of the establishment.
- The personnel unit or specialist who prepares the manpower plan should with the aid of the job description and job analysis, identify the corporate training needs. This will help to strengthen weak points of workers and improve their performance which will help in the developing of their potentials and prepare them for promotions to higher positions.
- Adequate promotion and re-absorption of trained agents should be encouraged in the public service.

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